

Stress Assessment Web App: A tool to assess academic stress, causes and effects on students in UTAS-Shinas

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Abstract:

In the world today, stress and depression are common emotional disorders that affect millions of people. Depressed people feel sad, lonely, helpless, lacking in energy, and losing interest in normal activities and hobbies due to signs of collapse and instability. Stress and depression are mental illnesses that affect the soul and the body, altering our thoughts and behaviours and leading to emotional and physical problems. Students are particularly susceptible to stress during this phase of their lives, and their mental health is impacted more often than anyone else's. Students in college are susceptible to stress because they are subjected to multiple pressures. These pressures can include family, psychological, educational, economic, or social pressures. These pressures cause them to feel anxious and exhausted because they are not living their normal lives, which leads to depression or stress. Consequently, it negatively impacts their academic performance and grade point average. In this project, we are primarily focused on developing a web application that will be used to detect depression and stress among students at UTAS Shinas. With this proposed application, we aim to provide accurate statistics for stress and depression levels for each semester of the academic year. To ensure that the assessment meets the international standards for depression, the Beck Depression Inventory is used as part of the assessment. A major benefit of this type of assessment is that it can both enhance the student life as well as their academic performance. The use of technology like this is intended to help students stay on top of their stress levels. It is also intended to eliminate the injuries they may experience as a result of stress. Furthermore, the proposed application will be totally free, and it won't require an email address to take the assessment or view the results. Moreover, the content of the website will never contain any advertisements. As part of the system, some guidance will be provided as well as some steps that students may follow to reduce their stress and depression. This application consists of a front-end user which can be accessed through any browser and a back-end user which can be presented through PHP language and WAMP server. A promising outcome is expected to be obtained from this project.

